

DIFFERENCES IN NUTRITION OF CHILDREN WITH DENTAL CARIES AND HEALTHY CHILDREN

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In the article, in order to improve the physical development and health of children and adolescents in our region, by enriching the composition of food products with supplements with biologically active substances, through diet Prevention of dental caries and other diseases caused by sweets is scientifically justifie.

Key words: biological nutrition, sweets, children's nutrition, biologically active substances.

Nowadays, the issue of promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, medical development of healthy nutrition, raising the medical culture of citizens in this field is on the minds of not only our country, but the entire world public. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), today 2 billion people (25-26%) on our planet do not consume enough organic micronutrients, such as iron and vitamin A, which are essential for the human body. Due to this, the growth and development of most children is delayed, they suffer from chronic tooth decay and dental caries. The main reason for this is a lack of healthy eating and lifestyle. The purpose of the study is to improve the diet and dental caries in children by enriching the content of food and confectionery products to be consumed in preschool children's institutions with supplements with biologically active substances. is to scientifically prove effective methods of disease prevention.

Research tasks: - assessment of the composition of confectionery products in the diet of preschool children's institutions and their role in the development of dental caries;
- analysis of the nutritional and biological importance of diet among children of preschool age and 3-7 years old who do not attend preschool;
- fight against dental caries caused by enriching the content of sweets with biologically active substances.

We got acquainted with the nutritional status of children from 4 to 7 years of age in preschool institutions in our region who are in 8-10 hours of preschool education in families.

The analysis of the materials on the actual nutritional characteristics of the studied age groups shows that the nutrition of children in kindergarten has a number of deviations from hygiene requirements. At the same time, according to the data obtained on the actual nutritional characteristics of the studied experimental groups, it was found that the nutrition of children in kindergartens has a number of shortcomings from a hygienic point of view. First, there are serious miscalculations in the nutrition of children attending preschool institutions, as a result of which significant errors were made from the recommended nutritional standards.

Second, the variety of foods in the recommended diet is limited. The food menu should be made according to the set of products that can fully cover the biological needs of the body,

taking into account the principles of proper nutrition. Menus in kindergartens are dominated by dishes made from cereals and pasta products. There is no diet in any of the children's institutions. The practice of fortification of prepared foods has been stopped almost everywhere. The issues of providing childcare institutions with special children's food products enriched with vitamins and trace elements have not been fully resolved. One of the reasons for the unsatisfactory organization of meals in kindergartens is that local authorities are not aware of children's health, the activities of children's institutions are not sufficiently monitored, and they are not funded in time and at the required level. meeting the need for food products in pre-school children's institutions is mainly carried out at the expense of bread, cereals and pasta products. Thus, the total amount of proteins in these products is 66-68%, carbohydrates -63-68%, and the calorie content is 50.1-50.3% due to bread, cereal and pasta products, 18.4-21.1% vegetable oil, 12% is made at the expense of meat, milk, vegetables. According to the results of the analysis of the actual nutritional status of children in families and preschool institutions, more than 46% have vitamin C, more than 50% have protein, A -84%; B6-46%; B12-by 78%; D showed deficiency up to -84%; minerals: calcium by 55%, phosphorus by 44%, magnesium by 62%; essential amino acids: methionine by -67%; It was found that leucine is 45% less, and amino acids involved in the formation of hemoglobin, bone tissue and brain cells are 86% less. Differences found in energy and nutrient consumption with the comparative results of the main biologically active substances in average daily diets in comparison with the actual content in average daily diets are explained by the incompleteness of rational nutrition standards in the organization of children's nutrition.

Conclusion: 1. When comparing the energy and nutritional value of the average daily ration of children (family meals in pre-school children's institutions), the quality of food products does not meet hygienic requirements in many respects.

2. According to the results of the analysis of the actual nutritional status of children in families and preschool institutions, vitamins A, B6, B12, C, D, protein, minerals: calcium, phosphorus, magnesium; amino acids: it was found that there are significant differences in the composition of substances such as methionine, leucine, hemoglobin, amino acids involved in the formation of bone tissue and brain cells.

3. The results of the study of the compositional structure of average daily diets for 4-6-year-old children revealed a lack of biological diversity and biologically active substances in dietary foods.

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